

LOAD FREQUENCY CONTROL IN A SINGLE AREA POWER SYSTEM USING OPTIMAL CONTROL DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of load frequency control is to minimise the transient variations and also to make sure that steady state errors is zero. Many modern control techniques are used to implement a reliable controller. The objective of these control techniques is to produce and deliver power reliably by maintaining both voltage and frequency within permissible range. This thesis studies the reliability of various control techniques of load frequency control of the proposed system through simulation in the MATLAB-Simulink environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Good quality of electrical power system means both the voltage and frequency to be fixed at desired values irrespective of change in loads that occurs randomly. It is in fact impossible to maintain both active and reactive power without control which would result in variation of voltage and frequency levels. To cancel the effect of load variation and to keep frequency and voltage level constant a control system is required. Though the active and reactive powers have a combined effect on the frequency and voltage, the control problem of the frequency and voltage can be separated. Frequency is mostly dependent on the active power and voltage is mostly dependent on the reactive power. The most important task of LFC is to maintain the

frequency constant against the varying active power loads, which is also referred as un- known external disturbance.

2. LOAD FREQUENCY CONTROL:

2.1 LOAD FREQUENCY PROBLEMS:

If the system is connected to numerous loads in a power system, then the system frequency and speed change with the characteristics of the governor as the load changes. If it's not required to maintain the frequency constant in a system then the operator is not required to change the setting of the generator. But if constant frequency is required the operator can adjust the velocity of the turbine by changing the characteristics of the governor when required. If a change in load is taken care by two generating stations running parallel then the complex nature of the system increases.

2.2. SPEED GOVERNING SYSTEM:

2.2.1 MATHEMATICAL MODELLING OF A GENERATOR:

With the use of swing equation of a synchronous machine to small perturbation, we have